

INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP PRACTICES AND INSTRUCTIONAL COMPETENCE OF MASTER TEACHERS IN THE SCHOOLS DIVISION OF IMUS CITY: BASIS FOR MASTER TEACHERS LEARNING AND DEVELOPMENT PLAN

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ABSTRACT

The study determined the instructional leadership practices and instructional competence of master teachers to come up with a learning and development plan that will lead to the improvement of the teaching and learning outcome in the Schools Division of Imus City. It utilized the descriptive-correlational design to describe the relationship of leadership practices and instructional competence of master teachers in the Schools Division of Imus City. Results revealed that the demographic profile of the master teachers, majority of them are female, aged 41 to 49, most them have doctorate units with specialization in science and mathematics, have 6 to 10 years length of service, have attended instructional leadership trainings of 47 hours and below, and have outstanding performance in their IPCRF. Based on the results, master teachers often practiced all the domains in the instructional leadership practices. While the level instructional competence of master teachers are highly competent. Moreover, the dominant domain in the instructional leadership practices of master teachers based on the computed results Personal Growth and Professional Development. While the dominant domain in the instructional competence is classroom management skills. The instructional leadership practices have no significant difference with sex, age educational attainment, field of specialization, length of service, and performance. However in terms of training hours, there is a significant difference. Furthermore, the instructional competence of master teachers have no significant difference with sex, age, educational attainment, field of specialization, length of service, training hours and performance. Finally, the instructional leadership practices and instructional competence of master teacher are highly related.

Keywords: *instructional leadership, competence, master teachers*

INTRODUCTION

Master teachers are intended to have greater expertise in curriculum development, professional development, and mentorship than typical teachers; they serve as role models for all other instructional staff and are regarded as the "gold standard" in education (National Institute for Excellence in Teaching cited in Moore, 2015). They are the "cream of the crop" in the teaching profession, and their teaching methods will differ from those of non-master instructors. (Ibrahim et al., 2013).

In addition, Master Teachers are individuals who have superior preparation, great teaching tactics, motivation and communication skills, strong curricular knowledge, interpersonal competence, and classroom management proficiencies, according to McClean (2009). Furthermore, Master Teachers are seen as competent teachers, staff developers, stimulants of curricular leadership, and good instructional leaders.

According to The Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers, which is built on NCBTS, complements the reform initiatives on teacher quality from pre-service education to in-service training. It articulates what constitutes teacher quality in the K to 12 Reform through well-defined domains, strands, and indicators that provide measures of professional learning, competent practice, and effective engagement. This set of standards makes explicit what teachers should know, be able to do and value to achieve competence, improved student learning outcomes, and eventually quality education. It is founded on teaching philosophies of learner-centeredness, lifelong learning, and inclusivity/inclusiveness, among others. The professional standards, therefore, become a public statement of professional accountability that can help teachers reflect on and assess their own practices as they aspire for personal growth and professional development.

Furthermore, DepEd Order (DO), No. 42, s. 2017 or the National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) recognizes the importance of professional standards in the continuing professional development and advancement of teachers based on the principle of lifelong learning. It is committed to supporting teachers, and taking cognizance of unequivocal evidence that good teachers are vital to raising student achievement. Quality learning is contingent upon quality teaching. Hence enhancing teacher quality becomes of utmost importance for long term and sustainable nation building.

DepEd Order (DO) No. 2, s. 2015 prescribes the guidelines on the establishment and Implementation of the Result- Based Performance Management System (RPMS) in the Department of Education and pursuant to Section 5 of DO 42, s. 2017 on the National Adaption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers, (PPST) which mandates that all performance of teachers shall be based on this set of standards. Based on the PPST, Master Teacher is categorized into Career Stage 3 or Highly Proficient Teachers consistently display a high level of performance in their teaching practice. They manifest an in-depth and sophisticated understanding of the

teaching and learning process. They have high education-focused situation cognition, are more adept in problem solving and optimize opportunities gained from experience. Career Stage 3 Teachers work collaboratively with colleagues and provide them support and mentoring to enhance their learning and practice. They continually seek to develop their professional knowledge and practice by reflecting on their own needs, and those of their colleagues and students.

Moreover, in the implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), Master Teachers are tasked to give the rating on the over- all performance of the teachers for that certain school year. These include their teaching competence, professional development, community linkages as specified in the Individual Performance and Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) for all teachers. This will become an important parcel of their teaching career as this will help them if they seek for promotion. Moreover, the observation of classes were directed to the master teachers as well. They observe teachers, feedback them with their teaching performance and bring out the best in them through their coaching. This will be reflected in the Classroom Observation Tool (COT) which reflects the rating of the teacher in terms of their teaching competence and will then become one of the required Means of Verification (MOV) once their yearly rating will commence. In addition, master teachers initiate crafting of projects and programs that enhance the curriculum and improve the performance of the students.

In the current situation of the master teachers in the Schools Division of Imus City, teachers who are promoted as master teachers there are still indicators in the domains from the PPST that are need to be enhanced, based on the submitted results of the E-SAT or the RPMS Self-Assessment Tool for Master Teacher I-IV in Schools Division Office for school year 2021-2022, which consists of 19 items as basis for identifying the level of capability and level of priority for development of master teachers. These items are the required competencies for master teachers which are congruent with the Philippine K to 12 Reform and reflective of international teacher standards.

Thus, the researcher conducted this study to further determine the instructional leadership practices and instructional competence of master's teachers to come up with a learning and development plan that will lead to the improvement of the teaching and learning outcome in the Schools Division of Imus City.

Research Questions

1. What is the demographic profile of the master teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1 sex,
 - 1.2 age,
 - 1.3 highest educational attainment,
 - 1.4 field of specialization,
 - 1.5 length of service as master teacher,
 - 1.6 training hours attended in instructional leadership, and,
 - 1.7 IPCRF rating?
2. What is the instructional leadership practices of the participants as assessed by themselves, school heads and teachers in terms of:

- 2.1 content, knowledge and pedagogy,
 - 2.2 learning environment,
 - 2.3 diversity of learners,
 - 2.4 curriculum and planning,
 - 2.5 assessment and reporting,
 - 2.6 community linkages and professional engagement, and,
 - 2.7 personal growth and professional development?
3. What is the level of instructional competence of the master teachers as assessed by themselves, school heads and teachers in terms of:
 - 3.1 mastery of the subject matter,
 - 3.2 teaching strategy skills;
 - 3.3 classroom management skills, and,
 - 3.4 evaluation skills?
 4. What is the dominant domain in the instructional leadership practices of master teachers?
 5. What domain is dominant in the instructional competence of master teachers?
 6. Is there a significant difference on the following variables when grouped according to demographic profile:
 - 6.1 instructional leadership practices, and,
 - 6.2 instructional competence?
 7. Is there a significant relationship between the instructional leadership practices and instructional competence of the participants? and,
 8. Based from the findings of the study, what learning and development plan can be proposed to improve the instructional leadership practices and instructional competence of master teachers?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized quantitative descriptive-correlational design. According to Lappe (2000), descriptive- correlational design aims to describe the relationship among variables rather than to infer cause and effect relationships. Descriptive correlational studies are useful for describing one phenomenon related to another in situations where the researcher has no control over the independent variables, the variables that are believed to cause or influence the dependent or outcome variable.

The descriptive design used to describe the instructional leadership skills and instructional competence of master teachers School Division of Imus City. Significant difference between the instructional leadership practices and instructional competence of the participants when grouped according to demographic profile was also described. The correlational design was used to test if there is a relationship between the instructional leadership practices and instructional competence of the participants.

This study was conducted in the Schools Division of Imus City, particularly on its four (4) stand-alone senior high schools; Gen Juan Castañeda Senior High School, Gen Flaviano Yengko Senior High School, Gen Pantaleon Garcia Senior High School, and

Governor Juanito Reyes Remulla Senior High School.

Gen Juan Castañeda Senior High School is located at Barangay Anabu II-A, Imus City, Cavite. The school offers Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) and Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL).

Gen Flaviano Yengko is located at Barangay Pasong Buaya II, Imus City, Cavite. The school offers Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM), Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) and Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL).

Gen Pantaleon Garcia Senior High School is located at Barangay Malagasang I-G, City of Imus, Cavite. The school offers Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM), Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) and Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL).

Lastly, Governor Juanito Reyes Remulla Senior High School. It is located at Barangay Toclong II-B, Imus City, Cavite. The school offers Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) and Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL).

This study used the adapted survey-questionnaires. It is aligned with the PPST standard and Master Teachers RPMS.

It contains three parts. Part 1 the demographic profile which includes the sex, age, highest educational attainment, field of specialization, length of service as master teacher, and trainings attended in instructional leadership. Part II contains the instructional leadership style of the master teacher. Part III contains the instructional competence of the master teacher.

The Part 1 the Demographic Profile survey-questionnaire, it was only the master teachers who answered the survey. Whereas, Part II the Instructional Leadership Practices of Master Teachers and, Part III the Instructional Leadership Competence of Master Teachers were answered by the Master Teachers, School Head and Teachers I to III.

The research survey-questionnaire on instructional competence of master teacher is a standardized questionnaire adapted from Laude et.al. (2018) which was used in their study. It has undergone validation and reliability testing and utilized Cronbach's alpha. While the survey-questionnaire on instructional leadership practices of master teachers is based on the Philippine Professional Standard for Teachers (PPST). It was validated by the three experts in the field of research and educational management. This questionnaire has undergone reliability testing using the Cronbach's Alpha as statistical tool in determining the reliability status of the questions and evaluated with thirty (30) respondents as a pilot test. The concept is ideal for the study because it goes beyond simply collecting and tabulating data. The researcher asked permission from the authors prior to utilizing it.

The participants of the study were nineteen (19) Master Teachers of senior high schools, one hundred fifteen teachers (115) and four (4) school heads in the Schools

Division of Imus City. Table 1 present the participants of the study.

The study solely collected the demographic profile of the master teachers, while the master teachers themselves evaluated their own instructional leadership practices and instructional competence. On the other hand, both school heads and teachers participating in the study also evaluated the instructional leadership and instructional competence of the master teachers.

The researcher utilized the total enumeration to determine the number of the participants. Total enumeration is a type of purposive sampling technique where the researcher chooses to examine the entire population that has one or more shared characteristics. This kind of purposive sampling technique is commonly used to generate reviews of events or experiences, which is to say, it is common to studies of particular groups within larger populations (Crossman 2020).

This study used the following statistical tools to answer the problems: Frequency, Percentage, Median, Friedman Two-way ANOVA, Mann-Whitney Test, U- Test, Kruskal Wallis, One – Way ANOVA and Spearman Rank.

This study adhered ethical considerations on the conduct of the study and to the Republic Act 10173, also known as Data Privacy Act of 2012. An informed consent letter was sent to the participants. The researcher also informed the participants on the purpose of the study. Moreover, protection of the privacy of the research participants and adequate level of confidentiality was ensured. Furthermore, result and findings of this study will only be shared to research conferences and research journals. Lastly, participation of the respondents in this study was voluntary and they have the rights to withdraw from the study at any stage if they wish to do so.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Table 1

Distribution of the master teachers in terms of sex

SEX	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Male	7	37
Female	12	63
TOTAL	19	100

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the master teachers in terms of Sex. Based on the results of the frequency and percentage distribution of the demographic profile of master teachers in terms of sex, out of 19 master teachers of the four stand- alone senior high school of School Division of Imus City, 7 or 37 percent are male and 12 or 63% are female.

The result implies that majority of the master teachers are dominated by female

teachers. It can be inferred that female preferred to teach than male. Likewise, love teaching. The findings agree with Dhal (2021) that majority of the teaching workforce are women. According to his study, more women were confined to teaching due to no other alternatives. Moreover, women also show love for the profession and desire to work with children. Furthermore, it is generally easier to secure employment in teaching than other professions.

Table 2
Distribution of the master teachers in terms of age

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
40 and below	4	21
41 to 49	8	42
50 and above	7	37
TOTAL	19	100

Range = 36 to 56
Mean = 46.26
Standard Error = 1.445

Table 2 presents the demographic profile of the master teachers in terms of Age. Based on the results of the frequency and percentage distribution of the demographic profile of master teachers in terms of age 4 or 21% are age 40 below, 8 or 42% are in age 41 to 49, and there are 7 or 37% are in their 50 and above.

The results demonstrates that master teachers are already experienced teachers. They have worked hard for their position. It also revealed that majority of the master teachers are already in their middle age.

The findings are in harmony with Potane (2021) that master teacher position was earned by teachers who are older and have taught for a long period of time and experienced when it comes to teaching as profession.

Table 3
Distribution of the master teachers in terms of educational attainment

EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Master's Degree	5	26
With Doctorate Units	10	53
Doctorate Degree	4	21

TOTAL	19	100
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Table 3 shows the demographic profile of master teachers in terms of Educational Attainment. Based on the results of the frequency and percentage distribution of the demographic profile of master teachers in terms of educational attainment, 10 or 53 percent are with doctorate degree units and 4 or 21% are with doctorate degree.

The table revealed that all the master teachers finished their masters’ degree since it a requirement in senior high school as master teacher. The findings prove that the senior high schools in Schools Division of Imus City adheres to the DepEd Order No. 3, s. 2016 on Hiring Guidelines for Senior High School Teachers Teaching Position particularly master teachers that must be a Master’s degree in relevant strand/subject. In addition, educational attainment has given the highest point in the criteria for hiring qualified teachers.

It also implies that master teachers are continuing professional development since most of them have doctorate units.

Sangalang (2018) states that continuing professional development, passion to teaching, and accepting other related works can be an avenue for a teacher being mentored to be promoted to a higher position.

Moreover, Aquino et al. (2021) states that school heads who have obtained their doctorate degrees get a greater level of leadership practices than the holders of master's degrees.

Table 4
Distribution of the master teachers in terms of specialization

FIELD OF SPECIALIZATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Math and Science	12	63
Others	7	37
TOTAL	19	100

Table 4 presents the demographic profile of master teachers in terms of Specialization. Based on the results of the frequency and percentage distribution of the demographic profile of master teachers in terms of Field of specialization, most the master teachers have a specialization in mathematics and sciences with 12 or 63 percent. This is because all the senior high schools in Schools Division of Imus City offers Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) strand. Majority of the hired teacher are major in Math and Science.

The findings also imply that teachers are qualified to teach the strand they are offering. DepEd Order No. 3, s. 2016 states that all the subjects in any track/strand offered by the school can be taught by qualified teachers.

Table 5*Distribution of the master teachers in terms of length of service*

LENGTH OF SERVICE	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
5 and below years	3	16
6 to 10 years	9	47
11 to 15 years	4	21
16 and above years	3	16
TOTAL	19	100

Table 5 presents the demographic profile of master teachers in terms of Length of Service. Based on the results of the frequency and percentage distribution of the demographic profile of master teachers in terms of length of service. Majority of the master teachers or 9 or 47% have length of service of 6-10 years.

The findings infer that majority of the master teachers are new in the Department of Education. This is because most of them were from the Higher Education Institution (HEI). They were hired as Master Teachers when the K to 12 was implemented. Moreover, they were the displaced teachers of HEI as a result of the implementation of RA 10533 otherwise known as the “Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013”.

Furthermore, some of the master teachers were transferred from the Junior High School and few were newly hired.

The findings oppose Aquino et al. (2021) that teachers with shorter relevant experience showed poorer educational quality relative to those who spent more time in the school system. There are other factors affecting educational quality of a teacher.

Cordova and Linaugo (2022), teachers with longer teaching experience perform better. Experienced teachers are more capable of boosting academic performance than inexperienced teachers.

Table 6*Distribution of the master teachers in terms of training hours attended*

TRAINING HOURS ATTENDED	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
47 Hours and below	10	53
48 to 71 Hours	3	15
72 Hours and above	6	32
TOTAL	19	100

Table 6 presents the demographic profile of master teachers in terms of Training Hours Attended. Based on the results of the frequency and percentage distribution of the demographic profile of master teachers in terms of training hours, most of them, 10 or 53 percent have only 47 hours and below attended instructional leadership training.

According to Essien et al. (2016) paramount for the teacher to be able to function effectively is to be trained and acquire a professional certificate. In-service courses, seminars and workshops act on their capacity as extra-incentives to the teachers' know-how and further acquisition of working experience.

The findings implies that master teachers need to attend additional trainings in order for them to become more efficient and skilled when it comes to instructional leadership.

The findings agree with Echeche (2022), generally master teachers are teaching for 21 - 25 years now, but their service as master teachers is mostly for 6 - 10 years only. Their not - so - long service as master teacher is mirrored in their need for more training related to coaching and mentoring since most of them have only attended 3 - 4 trainings. This also in harmony with Laude et al. (2018) that master teachers have 5 times and below in attendance in trainings and seminars which means that majority of them need more trainings and seminars in the future in order to equip themselves with the necessary skills and knowledge in developing life-long learners.

Table 7
Distribution of the master teachers in terms of IPCRF rating

IPCRF PERFORMANCE RATING	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
2019- 2020		
Very Satisfactory	7	68
Outstanding	6	32
2020- 2021		
Very Satisfactory	7	37
Outstanding	12	63
2021- 2022		
Very Satisfactory	7	37
Outstanding	12	63

Table 7 presents the demographic profile of master teachers in terms of their IPCRF Rating. Based on the results of the frequency and percentage distribution of the demographic profile of master teachers in terms of IPCRF rating, the table reveals that school year 2020- 2021 and 2021 – 2022 majority of the master teachers obtained an outstanding performance. School year mentioned covers the pandemic, nevertheless, master teachers are found to be outstanding in their performance this is because

master teachers have a deep understanding of the subject matter and it can be claimed that they were able to quickly transition to online or hybrid teaching models during the pandemic and adjust their lesson plan accordingly and strong digital skills, allowing them to effectively utilize online learning platforms, communication tools, and educational software. Moreover, most of the master teachers were being tap by the Division Office and Regional Office to craft Learning Modules. In addition, they may have attended webinars, workshops, or online courses focused on effective remote teaching strategies, technology integration, and student engagement. This continuous learning mindset allowed them to stay ahead and adapt their practices during the pandemic.

Camahalan and Naparan (2022), teachers' performance refers to the performance level of teachers in their duties and responsibilities in the profession. This concept covers teachers' yearly performance ratings with the IPCRF as its basis. Teachers should always maintain good performance through the continuous development of skills, knowledge, and motivation. The findings show that the master teachers have performed well in their duties and responsibilities as master teachers.

The result agrees with Ülger et al. (2014) that acquired competencies are the foundation for quality and effective teaching and a requirement for achieving education goals outlined in the educational process in a specialty area. However, according to Mendoza and Bautista (2022) teachers' performance based on IPRCF rating will remain unchanged regardless of their instructional competency skills.

Table 8
Overall IPCRF rating of master teachers

IPCRF RATING	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Very Satisfactory	7	37
Outstanding	12	63

Table 8 presents the overall IPCRF Rating of master. Based on the results of the study, majority of the master teachers are outstanding in performance. It can be inferred that they possess exceptional skills, knowledge, and abilities in their field of teaching. They likely demonstrate a high level of competence and effectiveness in delivering instruction, engaging students, and achieving positive learning outcomes. Their outstanding performance suggests that they have mastered their craft and are capable of effectively facilitating student learning and development.

Table 9 presents the instructional leadership practices of master teachers in teachers in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy. The findings revealed that all the indicators in domain content knowledge and pedagogy, it obtain the median of 4. 00 and interpreted as *high extent*. Master teachers *often practiced* the indicators under this domain.

The study reveals that master teachers often practice these domains and demonstrates exemplary practices to teachers.

The findings agrees with Jacob et al. (2020) that the key hope from an educational improvement perspective is that the gains in teacher pedagogical content knowledge may lead to learning gains in students' achievement. A teacher with better content knowledge who knows how to teach the subject to a specific audience is expected to create student gains over a less prepared or a less experienced teacher.

Also, the findings is in harmony with with Widayati, MacCallum, & Woods-McConney (2021), that teachers should improve not only their content knowledge but also their pedagogical knowledge since students' achievements are largely associated with teachers' practice (pedagogical knowledge and skills).

It can be claimed that master teachers possess a comprehensive understanding of their content area. Their extensive knowledge and expertise enable them to effectively plan and deliver instruction, incorporating relevant and up-to-date information and resources. In addition, it is also evident that master teachers actively share their knowledge and expertise with other educators, providing guidance and support in content knowledge and pedagogy. Through collaborative efforts, they contribute to the professional growth and development of their colleagues.

Table 9
Instructional leadership practices of the Master Teachers in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy

ITEMS	MEDIAN	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy		
1. Model exemplary practice to improve the applications of content knowledge within and across curriculum teaching areas.	4.00	Often Practiced
2. Lead colleagues in the advancement of the art and science of teaching based on their comprehensive knowledge of research and pedagogy.	4.00	Often Practiced
3. Mentor colleagues in the implementation of policies to ensure the positive use of ICT within or beyond the school.	4.00	Often Practiced

4. Model a comprehensive selection of effective teaching strategies that promote learner achievement in literacy and numeracy.	4.00	Often Practiced
5. Lead colleagues in reviewing, modifying and expanding their range of teaching strategies that promote critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills.	4.00	Often Practiced
6. Show exemplary skills in and advocate the use of Mother Tongue, Filipino and English in teaching and learning To facilitate the learners' language, cognitive and academic development and to foster pride of their language, heritage and culture.	4.00	Often Practiced
7. Exhibit exemplary practice in the use of effective verbal and non-verbal classroom communication strategies to support learner understanding, participation, engagement and achievement in different learning contexts.	4.00	Often Practiced

	MEDIAN	4.00	OFTEN PRACTICED
Legend			
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low Extent	Never Practiced	
1.80 – 2.59	Low Extent	Seldom Practiced	
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extent	Occasionally Practiced	
3.40 – 4.19	High Extent	Often Practiced	
4.20 – 5.00	Very High Extent	Always Practiced	

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Table 10

Instructional leadership practices of the Master Teachers in terms of learning environment

ITEMS	MEDIAN	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
Learning Environment		
1. Apply comprehensive knowledge of and act as a resource person for, policies, guidelines and procedures that relate to the implementation of safe and secure learning environments for learners.	4.00	Often Practiced
2. Advocate and facilitate the use of effective practices to foster learning environments that promote fairness, respect and care to encourage learning.	4.00	Often Practiced
3. Model exemplary practices in the management of classroom structure and activities, and lead colleagues at the whole-school level to review and evaluate their practices.	4.00	Often Practiced
4. Facilitate processes to review the effectiveness of the school's learning environment to nurture and inspire learner participation.	4.00	Often Practiced
5. Lead and empower colleagues in promoting learning environments that effectively motivate learners to achieve quality outcomes by assuming responsibility for their own learning.	4.00	Often Practiced
6. Provide leadership in applying a wide range of strategies in the implementation of positive and non-	4.00	Often Practiced

violent discipline policies/ procedures to ensure learning-focused environments.

	MEDIAN	4.00	OFTEN PRACTICED
Legend			
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low Extent	Never Practiced	
1.80 – 2.59	Low Extent	Seldom Practiced	
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extent	Occasionally Practiced	
3.40 – 4.19	High Extent	Often Practiced	
4.20 – 5.00	Very High Extent	Always Practiced	

Table 10 presents the instructional leadership practices of master teachers in teachers in terms of Learning Environment. The findings revealed that all the indicators in domain learning environment, it obtains the median of 4.00 and interpreted as *high extent*. The results of the study reveal that master teachers *often practiced* the indicators in this domain.

The results agree with Echeche (2022) that coaching and mentoring practices in domain learning and environment are consistently demonstrated. Master Teachers are revealed to be moderately modeling a range of high - level skills on learning environment.

It is evident from the findings that master teachers possess a comprehensive understanding of the policies, guidelines, and procedures related to student safety and security. They utilize this knowledge to ensure the implementation of effective measures in their classrooms and act as valuable resources for their colleagues in promoting safe and secure learning environments for all learners.

Table 11

Instructional leadership practices of the master teachers in terms of diversity of learners

ITEMS	MEDIAN	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
Diversity of Learners		
1. Lead colleagues to evaluate differentiated strategies to enrich teaching practices that address learners' differences in gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences.	4.00	Often Practiced
2. Model exemplary teaching practices that recognize and affirm diverse linguistic, cultural, socioeconomic and religious backgrounds to promote learner success	4.00	Often Practiced

3. Lead colleagues in designing, adapting and implementing teaching strategies that are responsive to learners with disabilities, giftedness and talents.	4.00	Often Practiced
4. Model a range of high level skills responsive to the special educational needs of learners in difficult circumstances, including: geographic isolation; chronic illness; displacement due to armed conflict, urban resettlement or disasters; child abuse and child labor practices	4.00	Often Practiced
5. Show comprehensive skills in delivering culturally appropriate teaching strategies to address effectively the needs of learners from indigenous groups	4.00	Often Practiced

MEDIAN		4.00	OFTEN PRACTICED
Legend			
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low Extent	Never Practiced	
1.80 – 2.59	Low Extent	Seldom Practiced	
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extent	Occasionally Practiced	
3.40 – 4.19	High Extent	Often Practiced	
4.20 – 5.00	Very High Extent	Always Practiced	

Table 11 presents the instructional leadership practices of master teachers in teachers in terms of Diversity of Learners. The findings revealed that all the indicators in domain diversity of learners, it obtains the median of 4.00 and interpreted as *high extent*. It reveals that master teachers *often practiced* the indicators in this domain. Master Teachers are revealed to be moderately modeling a range of high - level skills responsive to the special educational needs of learners (Echeche, 2022).

Moreover, it can be claimed that master teachers take a leadership role in guiding their colleagues to evaluate and implement differentiated strategies that cater to learners' differences in gender, needs, strengths, interests, and experiences. They foster collaboration, share best practices, provide support, and promote ongoing reflection to create inclusive and effective teaching practices that address the diverse needs of all students.

Table 12

Instructional leadership practices of the master teachers in terms of curriculum and planning

ITEMS	MEDIAN	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
Curriculum and Planning		
1. Model exemplary practice and lead colleagues in enhancing current practices in the planning and management of developmentally sequenced teaching and learning process.	4.00	Often Practiced
2. Exhibit high-level skills and lead in setting achievable and challenging learning outcomes that are aligned with learning competencies towards the cultivation of a culture of excellence for all.	4.00	Often Practiced
3. Provide advice in the design and implementation of relevant and responsive learning programs that develop the knowledge and skills of learners at different ability levels.	4.00	Often Practiced
4. Lead colleagues in professional discussions to plan and implement strategies that enrich teaching practice.	4.00	Often Practiced
5. Model exemplary skills and lead colleagues in the development and evaluation of teaching and learning resources, including ICT, for use within and beyond the school.	4.00	Often Practiced
MEDIAN	4.00	OFTEN PRACTICED

Legend

1.00 – 1.79	Very Low Extent	Never Practiced
1.80 – 2.59	Low Extent	Seldom Practiced
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extent	Occasionally Practiced
3.40 – 4.19	High Extent	Often Practiced
4.20 – 5.00	Very High Extent	Always Practiced

Table 12 presents the instructional leadership practices of master teachers in teachers in terms of Curriculum and Planning. The findings revealed that all the indicators in domain curriculum and planning, it obtains the median of 4.00 and interpreted as *high extent*. It reveals that master teachers *often practiced* the indicators in this domain. The results approve the findings of Lucero (2018) that curriculum and planning are very extensively practiced and very evident to master teachers.

Moreover, it can be claimed that master teachers often practice domain, curriculum and planning. They take a leadership role in leading professional discussions that focus on planning and implementing strategies to enrich teaching practice. They create a collaborative and supportive environment where colleagues can share ideas, explore new approaches, and reflect on their teaching methods. By fostering professional growth and facilitating the implementation of effective strategies, master teachers contribute to the continuous improvement of teaching practice within their school or community.

Table 13

Instructional leadership practices of master teachers in terms of assessment and reporting

ITEMS	MEDIAN	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
Assessment and Reporting		
1. Lead initiatives in the evaluation of assessment policies and guidelines that relate to the design, selection, organization and use of effective diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements.	4.00	Often Practiced
2. Provide advice on, and mentor colleagues in the effective analysis and use of learner attainment data.	4.00	Often Practiced
3. Exhibit exemplary skills and lead initiatives to support colleagues in applying strategies that effectively provide timely, accurate and constructive feedback to learners to improve learning achievement.	4.00	Often Practiced
4. Share with colleagues a wide range of strategies that ensure effective communication of learner needs, progress and achievement to key stakeholders, including parents/guardians.	4.00	Often Practiced
5. Lead colleagues to explore, design and implement effective practices and programs using information derived from assessment data.	4.00	Often Practiced
MEDIAN	4.00	OFTEN PRACTICED

Legend

1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Extent Never Practiced
1.80 – 2.59	Low Extent	Seldom Practiced

2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extent	Occasionally Practiced
3.40 – 4.19	High Extent	Often Practiced
4.20 – 5.00	Very High Extent	Always Practiced

Table 13 presents the instructional leadership practices of master teachers in teachers in terms of Assessment and Reporting. The findings revealed that all the indicators in domain assessment and reporting, it obtains the median of 4.00 and interpreted as *high extent*. It reveals that master teachers *often practiced* the indicators in this domain.

The result of the study agrees with Lucero (2018) that the teachers promote learning and growth of all students by designing and administering authentic and meaningful student assessments and analyzing performance to help in refine learning objectives. Master teachers are fully capable of organizing lessons, evaluating student performance, and informing parents of that performance as part of their job responsibilities (Podador, 2023).

It can be claimed that master teachers recognize the importance of effective assessment practices in promoting student learning, and they actively seek ways to improve the assessment system within their school. Moreover, master teachers exhibit exemplary skills and lead initiatives to support colleagues in applying effective feedback strategies demonstrate strong instructional leadership, expertise in feedback practices, learner-centered approaches, commitment to continuous improvement, impact on learning achievement, and collaboration with colleagues. Their efforts contribute to creating a culture of effective feedback that enhances learning outcomes for students and promotes professional growth among teachers.

Table 14

Instructional leadership practices of the master teachers in terms of community linkages and professional engagement

Items	Median	Verbal Interpretation
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement		
1. Model exemplary practice and empower colleagues to establish and maintain effective learning environments that are responsive to community contexts.	4.00	Often Practiced
2. Lead in consolidating networks that strengthen relationships with parents/guardians and the wider school community to maximize their involvement in the educative process.	4.00	Often Practiced

3. Lead colleagues in the regular review of existing codes, laws and regulations that apply to the teaching profession, and the responsibilities as specified in the Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers.	4.00	Often Practiced
4. Evaluate existing school policies and procedures to make them more responsive to the needs of the learners, parents and other stakeholders.	4.00	Often Practiced

MEDIAN	4.00	OFTEN PRACTICED
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Legend

1.00 – 1.79	Very Low Extent	Never Practiced
1.80 – 2.59	Low Extent	Seldom Practiced
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extent	Occasionally Practiced
3.40 – 4.19	High Extent	Often Practiced
4.20 – 5.00	Very High Extent	Always Practiced

Table 14 presents the instructional leadership practices of master teachers in teachers in terms of Community Linkages and Professional Engagement. The findings revealed that all the indicators in domain Community Linkages and Professional Engagement, it obtains the median of 4.00 and interpreted as *high extent*. It reveals that master teachers *often practiced* the indicators in this domain.

The findings agree with Echeche (2022), Master Teachers demonstrate strength in interpersonal relationship and leading in community linkages activities. However, the findings oppose (Lucero 2018), that there is need to strengthen the mentoring of teachers on school-community partnership such as encouraging parents to regularly visit the school to follow-up on learners’ performance.

It can be claimed that master teachers demonstrate exemplary teaching, support their colleagues in creating effective learning environments, build relationships with parents and the wider community, and guide their colleagues in understanding and fulfilling their professional responsibilities.

Table 15

Instructional leadership practices of the master teachers in terms of personal growth and professional development

ITEMS	MEDIAN	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
Personal Growth and Professional Development		
1. Model a learner-centered teaching philosophy through teaching practices that stimulate colleagues to engage in further professional learning.	4.00	Often Practiced

2. Act as a role model and advocate for upholding the dignity of teaching as a profession to build a positive teaching and learning culture within and beyond the school.	4.00	Often Practiced
3. Take a leadership role in supporting colleagues' engagement with professional networks within and across schools to advance knowledge and practice in identified areas of need.	4.00	Often Practiced
4. Demonstrate leadership within and across school contexts in critically evaluating practice and setting clearly defined targets for professional development.	4.00	Often Practiced
5. Lead reforms in enhancing professional development programs based on an in-depth knowledge and understanding of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers.	4.00	Often Practiced

MEDIAN	4.00	OFTEN PRACTICED
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Legend

1.00 – 1.79	Very Low Extent	Never Practiced
1.80 – 2.59	Low Extent	Seldom Practiced
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extent	Occasionally Practiced
3.40 – 4.19	High Extent	Often Practiced
4.20 – 5.00	Very High Extent	Always Practiced

Table 15 presents the instructional leadership practices of master teachers in teachers in terms of Personal Growth and Professional Development. The findings revealed that all the indicators in domain Personal Growth and Professional Development, it obtains the median of 4.00 and interpreted as *high extent*. It reveals that master teachers *often practiced* the indicators in this domain.

The results of the study agree with Lucero (2018) that teachers are extensively involved in professional growth and are extensively active in pursuing the professional development and learning opportunities to improve quality of practice or build the expertise and experience to assume different instructional and leadership role. By attending trainings and seminars, enrolling in graduate programs for their professional development, and upgrading themselves, they have presumably enhanced their personal growth and increased their level of competition in their area of competence (Podador, 2023).

It can be claimed that master teachers actively engage in continuous learning and improvement to enhance their teaching practice. Additionally, they exemplify best practices and inspire their colleagues to engage in personal growth and professional

development.

Table 16

Overall result of instructional leadership practices of the master teachers

INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP PRACTICES DOMAINS	MEDIAN	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	4.00	Often Practiced
Learning Environment	4.00	Often Practiced
Diversity of Learners	4.00	Often Practiced
Curriculum and Planning	4.00	Often Practiced
Assessment and Reporting	4.00	Often Practiced
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	4.00	Often Practiced
Personal Growth and Development	4.00	Often Practiced
MEDIAN	4.00	OFTEN PRACTICED
Legend		
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low Extent	Never Practiced
1.80 – 2.59	Low Extent	Seldom Practiced
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extent	Occasionally Practiced
3.40 – 4.19	High Extent	Often Practiced
4.20 – 5.00	Very High Extent	Always Practiced

Table 16 presents the overall result of the instructional leadership practices of master teachers. The findings revealed that all the domains of the instructional leadership competence of master teachers obtain a median of 4.00 which is interpreted as *highly extent*. Master teachers *often practiced* the indicators in the domains of the PPST.

The findings suggest that master teachers possess a high level of instructional leadership competence across all domains. They demonstrate expertise in various aspects of instructional leadership, effectively contribute to student learning, and can serve as valuable resources for their colleagues.

Table 17

Level of instructional competence of the master teachers in terms of mastery of the subject matter

ITEMS	MEDIAN	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
Mastery of the Subject Matter		
1. Comprehensive and accurate grasp of the subject matter.	4.50	Highly Competent
2. Relates subject matter to other fields of knowledge	4.00	Competent
3. Integrates subject matter with relevant topics.	4.00	Competent
4. Enrich discussions with contemporary issues and events.	4.00	Competent
5. Answers students' inquiry intelligently and to the point.	4.00	Competent
6. Provides varied learning experience for the intellectual development.	4.00	Competent
7. Provides intelligent resolution of the students' questions.	4.00	Competent
8. Possesses the skill in the science and art of motivation.	4.00	Competent
9. Explains difficult concepts well.	4.00	Competent
10. Provides appropriate reinforcement.	4.00	Competent
11. Manifests confidence and firmness with every information being given in the class.	4.00	Competent
12. Emphasizes difficult parts of the lesson easy to understand.	4.00	Competent
13. Explains the lesson by citing relevant examples and situations.	4.00	Competent
14. Readily defines important terms in the lesson.	4.00	Competent
15. Relates subject matter to previous topics and areas of interest.	4.00	Competent
16. Is able to relate lesson to other subjects.	4.00	Competent
17. Answer questions clearly with confidence.	4.00	Competent

18. Cites current and timely information on the subject.	4.00	Competent
19. Show a full grasp of the lesson taught each day.	4.00	Competent
20. Reflects mastery of the entire subject he/she teaches.	4.00	Competent
MEDIAN	4.00	COMPETENT
Legend		
1.00 – 1.79	Never	Not Competent
1.80 – 2.59	Seldom	Slightly Competent
2.60 – 3.39	Sometimes	Moderately Competent
3.40 – 4.19	Often	Competent
4.20 – 5.00	Always	Highly Competent

Table 18 presents the level of instructional competence of master teachers in terms of Mastery of the Subject Matter. The findings revealed that the indicators “*Comprehensive and accurate grasp of the subject matter*” obtain a median of 4.50 and interpreted as highly competent. The rest of the indicators obtain a median of 4.00 and interpreted as competent. The results can be inferred that master teachers have developed competencies beyond simple facts or surface-level comprehension.

The results agree with Podador (2023) that in order to facilitate learning in the students, master teachers used a variety of teaching techniques and integrated examples and learning situations.

Master teachers utilized varied teaching strategies and integrate examples and learning situations in order to effect learning to the students. In addition, they are also practicing the localization and contextualization of the curriculum which is beneficial to the students since they can relate the lesson to their community (Laude, Ralar, & Arcenal, 2018).

The findings indicate that master teachers have a highly competent grasp of the subject matter. They possess a strong command of the content, effectively convey it to students, apply their expertise in instructional practices, and are well-equipped to address students' questions and challenges. This high level of subject matter competence contributes to their overall effectiveness in teaching and facilitating student learning.

Table 18

Level of instructional competence of the master teachers in terms of teaching strategy skills

ITEMS	MEDIAN	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
Teaching Strategy Skills		
1. Organizes and presents subject matter clearly and coherently.	4.00	Competent
2. Communicate ideas effective in English/Filipino fluently.	4.00	Competent
3. Presents the lesson systematically and analytically.	4.00	Competent
4. Stimulates thinking and clarify lessons through effective questions.	4.00	Competent
5. Adjust teaching methods to students' needs, interest and abilities.	4.00	Competent
6. Uses variety of teaching techniques, approaches and strategies to make the lesson interesting and meaningful.	4.00	Competent
7. Utilizes ICT instruction in delivering the lesson to the students	4.00	Competent
8. Encourages students to ask questions and to express their own point of view.	4.00	Competent
9. Provides challenging tasks, problems and assignments.	4.00	Competent
10. Selects, prepares and utilizes instructional materials effectively in achieving teaching objectives.	4.00	Competent
11. Uses language effectively in expressing ideas in class discussion.	4.00	Competent
12. Encourages the students to think and clarify lessons through effective questioning towards the students.	4.00	Competent
13. Adjust teaching methods to students' needs, interests, and activities.	4.00	Competent
14. Uses different teaching techniques, approaches and strategies to make the lesson interesting and meaningful	4.00	Competent

15. Relates lesson to the existing conditions and real life situation convincingly	4.00	Competent
16. Utilizes instructional materials that sustains students' attention in achieving teaching objectives.	4.00	Competent
17. Is able to utilize activities that are helpful for students to understand the lesson.	4.00	Competent
18. Motivates the students by asking questions effectively to develop critical thinking and creativity.	4.00	Competent
MEDIAN	4.00	COMPETENT
Legend		
1.00 – 1.79	Never	Not Competent
1.80 – 2.59	Seldom	Slightly Competent
2.60 – 3.39	Sometimes	Moderately Competent
3.40 – 4.19	Often	Competent
4.20 – 5.00	Always	Highly Competent

Table 18 presents the level of instructional competence of master teachers in term of Teaching Strategy Skills. The findings revealed that all the indicators in teaching strategy skills, it obtain the median of 4.00 and interpreted as competent.

The results agree with Paciona (2019) that teachers give time and effort in analyzing and sequencing activities on the subject matter for the students to master the lessons.

The results of the study agree with Laude et al. (2018) that master teachers strategically utilized varied methods of teaching in order for the students to develop their thinking ability skills, thus making them more creative and focused to the topics presented during the teaching-learning process.

The “*competent*” interpretation suggests that master teachers can adapt their teaching strategies to suit different instructional contexts and student characteristics. They are flexible in their approach, considering factors such as classroom dynamics, diverse learning styles, and individual student needs, to maximize the effectiveness of the chosen strategies.

Table 19

Level of instructional competence of the master teachers in terms of classroom management skills

ITEMS	MEDIAN	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
Classroom Management Skills		
1. Commands respect from the students.	4.00	Competent
2. Prepares adequately for the day's learning activities.	4.50	Highly Competent
3. Ensures cleanliness and orderliness in class	4.00	Competent
4. Is keen about healthy and balanced instruction with students.	4.00	Competent
5. Utilizes class periods productively	4.00	Competent
6. Awakens and maintains students' interest in the lessons and class discussion.	4.00	Competent
7. Administers test effectively and returns corrected papers and other students' work promptly	4.00	Competent
8. Achieves teaching objectives to the optimum degree possible for the particular subject, lesson, or activity within a reasonable time frame	4.00	Competent
9. Handles disciplinary problem effectively.	4.00	Competent
10. Makes classroom atmosphere cordial and cooperative to enhance the learning process.	5.00	Highly Competent
11. Shows a great deal of patience towards the students	4.00	Competent
12. Starts learning activities on time	4.00	Competent
13. Comes to class early and leaves on time.	4.50	Highly Competent
14. Makes every moment in class active promoting fun about learning.	4.00	Competent

15. Sustains students' interest in the lesson and class discussion.	4.00	Competent
16. Establishes authority in the classroom effectively by making students obey rules set forth.	4.00	Competent
17. Helps the class achieve the objectives set for the day.	5.00	Highly Competent
18. Makes the students behave according to how they are expected to.	5.00	Highly Competent
19. Is able to assist students in doing cooperative group tasks.	4.50	Highly Competent

	MEDIAN	5.00	HIGHLY COMPETENT
Legend			
1.00 – 1.79	Never	Not Competent	
1.80 – 2.59	Seldom	Slightly Competent	
2.60 – 3.39	Sometimes	Moderately Competent	
3.40 – 4.19	Often	Competent	
4.20 – 5.00	Always	Highly Competent	

Table 19 presents the level of instructional competence of master teachers in terms of Classroom Management Skills. The findings revealed that the indicators “*Makes classroom atmosphere cordial and cooperative to enhance the learning process.*”, “*Helps the class achieve the objectives set for the day.*” and “*Makes the students behave according to how they are expected to*” obtain a median of 5.00 and interpreted as highly competent. While the indicator “*Prepares adequately for the day’s learning activities.*” obtain a median of 4.50 and interpreted as highly competent. The rest of the indicators obtain a median of 4.00 and interpreted as competent.

The results of the study confirm the findings of Collins (2022) that students taught by more experienced teachers achieve at a higher level because their teachers have mastered the content and acquired classroom management skills/expertise to deal with various types of classroom problems. Moreover, according to the study, it is not only mastering of the subject area result in effective teaching, but this also should be accompanied by effective communication.

The results are in harmony with Podador (2023) that master teachers had complete control inside the classroom because learners behaved appropriately while participating in pre-planned activities.

The findings indicate that master teachers are highly competent in creating a positive and cooperative classroom atmosphere, guiding students towards daily objectives, and promoting appropriate student behavior. Their expertise in these areas contributes to

the establishment of a conducive learning environment that supports student engagement, achievement, and overall academic success.

Table 20

Level of instructional competence of master teachers in terms of evaluation skills

ITEMS	MEDIAN	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
Evaluation Skills		
1. Evaluates students' performances fairly and uses adequate and accurate standards measures of evaluation.	4.00	Competent
2. Selects and utilizes criterion referenced tests.	4.00	Competent
3. Analyzes and interprets evaluation results skillfully.	4.00	Competent
4. Utilizes evaluation result as a basis for improving instruction.	4.00	Competent
5. Uses varied forms of evaluation tools.	4.00	Competent
6. Evaluates performance of the students on the basis of the course objectives through discussions, quizzes, and major examinations	4.00	Competent
7. Gives grades on the basis of students' performance.	5.00	Highly Competent
8. Treats each student fair and square.	4.50	Highly Competent
9. Exercises no favoritism.	4.50	Highly Competent
10. Acts according to own intellectual judgment.	4.00	Competent
11. Provides evaluative activities appropriate to students' abilities, interest, and needs.	4.00	Competent
12. Gives evaluation result ratings that are well-accepted by the students.	4.00	Competent
13. Utilizes evaluation result as a basis for improving instruction.	4.00	Competent

14. Uses different methods in evaluating students' learning aligned to the learning objectives such as oral performance, projects, hands-on and etc.	4.00	Competent
15. Includes items in the tests that are based on lesson objectives consisted with actual discussions activities and classroom interactions	4.00	Competent
16. Gives grades on the basis of students' actual performance.	5.00	Highly Competent
17. Treats each student fairly in giving grades.	5.00	Highly Competent
18. Bases ratings according to the objectives of the lessons and criteria set in class.	5.00	Highly Competent
19. Allows students to rate their own performances in some of the activities in the class.	4.00	Competent

MEDIAN		4.00	COMPETENT
Legend			
1.00 – 1.79	Never	Not Competent	
1.80 – 2.59	Seldom	Slightly Competent	
2.60 – 3.39	Sometimes	Moderately Competent	
3.40 – 4.19	Often	Competent	
4.20 – 5.00	Always	Highly Competent	

Table 20 presents the level of instructional competence of master teachers in terms of Evaluation Skills. The findings revealed that the indicators, “*Gives grades on the basis of students’ performance.*”, “*Gives grades on the basis of students’ actual performance.*”, “*Treats each student fairly in giving grades.*”, and “*Bases ratings according to the objectives of the lessons and criteria set in class.*” obtain a median of 5.00 and interpreted as highly competent. While the indicators “*Treats each student fair and square.*” and “*Exercises no favoritism.*” obtain a median of 4.50 and interpreted as highly competent. The rest of the indicators obtain a median of 4.00 and interpreted as competent. The findings implies that master teachers manifest fairness in evaluating students’ performance.

The results of the study agree with Podador (2023) that master teachers used authentic assessment in assigning grades to students. Master teachers did not establish partiality in the way they graded their students.

It can be claimed that that master teachers are highly competent in giving grades based

on students' performance, treating each student fairly, aligning grades with learning objectives and class criteria, and assessing students' performance accurately. Their proficiency in these areas contributes to the integrity and credibility of the grading process and supports students' understanding of their progress and achievement in the classroom.

Table 21

Overall result of the level of instructional competence of master teachers

INSTRUCTIONAL COMPETENCE	MEDIAN	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
Mastery of the Subject Matter	4.00	Competent
Teaching Strategy Skills	4.00	Competent
Classroom Management Skills	5.00	Highly Competent
MEDIAN	4.00	HIGH EXTENT

Table 21 presents the overall result of the level of instructional competence of master teachers. The findings revealed that “*classroom management skills*” obtain a median of 5.00 which is interpreted as highly competent, while the rest competencies obtain a median of 4.00 which is interpreted as competent.

The result of the study can be claimed that master teachers are experienced teachers when it comes to managing the class. They are equipped with techniques and strategies on how to deal with various types of classroom problems.

The findings indicate that master teachers exhibit exceptional competence in classroom management skills and solid competence in other domains. This combination of high competency in classroom management and overall competence in other areas positions master teachers as effective educators who can establish a positive learning environment and demonstrate proficiency in various aspects of teaching practice.

Table 22

Dominant domain in the instructional leadership practices according to master teachers, school head and teachers

PARTICIPANTS	INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP PRACTICES	MEAN RANK	RANK	FRIEDMAN STATISTICS	P VALUE	REMARKS
Master Teacher	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	3.50 ab	6	18.857	0.00 4	Reject Ho

Table 23. Continued.

Learning Environment	3.82 ab	5
Diversity of Learners	3.26 b	7
Curriculum Planning	3.87 ab	4
Assessment and Reporting	4.61 ab	2
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	4.21 ab	3
Personal Growth and Professional Development	4.74 a	1

School Heads	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	5.63	1	7.588	0.27 0	Accept Ho
	Learning Environment	3.00	7			
	Diversity of Learners	3.75	3.25			
	Curriculum Planning	3.75	3.25			
	Assessment and Reporting	4.38	2			
	Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	3.75	3.25			
	Personal Growth and Professional Development	3.75	3.25			

	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	4.07 ab	3			
	Learning Environment	4.41 a	1			
	Diversity of Learners	3.81 ab	6			
Teachers	Curriculum Planning	3.95 ab	4	17.576	0.00 7	Reject Ho
	Assessment and Reporting	3.94 ab	5			
	Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	3.72 b	7			
	Personal Growth and Professional Development	4.09 ab	2			
	CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND PEDAGOGY	4.04 AB	4			
	LEARNING ENVIRONMENT	4.29 A	1			
	DIVERSITY OF LEARNERS	3.74 B	7			
TOTAL	CURRICULUM PLANNING	3.93 AB	6	16.599	0.01 1	REJECT HO
	ASSESSMENT AND REPORTING	4.05 AB	3			
	COMMUNITY LINKAGES AND PROFESSIONAL ENGAGEMENT	3.79 AB	5			

PERSONAL GROWTH AND PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT	4.17 AB	2
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Mean rank followed by a common letter are not significant at 5% level

Table 22 shows the dominant domain in the instructional leadership practices of master teachers. It reveals that based on the self-assessment of master teacher-participants, their dominant domain in the instructional leadership practices is *personal growth and professional development* with mean rank of 4.74 and is rank, *first*. It is evident in the result that master teachers model a learner-centered teaching philosophy through teaching practices that stimulate colleagues to engage in further professional learning, act as role model and advocate for upholding the dignity of teaching as a profession to build a positive teaching and learning culture within and beyond the school, take a leadership role in supporting colleagues' engagement with professional networks within and across schools to advance knowledge and practice in identified areas of need, demonstrate leadership within and across school contexts in critically evaluating practice and setting clearly defined targets for professional development, and lead reforms in enhancing professional development programs based on an in-depth knowledge and understanding of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers.

According to school heads, the dominant domain in the instructional leadership practices of master teachers is *content knowledge and pedagogy* with mean rank of 5.63, and is rank, *first*. This domain is dominant according to school heads since they are the ones who observe master teachers. It is evident based on the result as observe by the schools heads that, master teachers model exemplary practice to improve the applications of content knowledge within and across curriculum teaching areas, lead colleagues in the advancement of the art and science of teaching based on their comprehensive knowledge of research and pedagogy, mentor colleagues in the implementation of policies to ensure the positive use of ICT within and beyond the school, model a comprehensive selection of effective teaching strategies that promote learner achievement in literacy and numeracy, lead colleagues in reviewing, modifying and expanding their range of teaching strategies that promote critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher- order thinking skills, show exemplary skills in an and advocate the use of mother tongue, Filipino and English in teaching and learning to facilitate the learners' language, cognitive and academic development and to foster pride of their language, heritage and culture, and exhibit exemplary practice in the use of effective verbal and non-verbal classroom communication strategies to support learner understanding, participation, engagement and achievement in different learning contexts.

According to teachers, the dominant domain of instructional leadership practices of master teachers is *learning environment* with the mean rank of 4.41 and is rank, *first*. This is evident based on the observation of the teachers since master teachers are the ones who give technical assistance to teachers, they serve as resource speaker during the Learning Action Cell and In-Service Training and master teachers serve as demonstration

teachers. Therefore evidently, these indicators are observed by the teachers. Apply comprehensive knowledge of and act as a resource person for, policies, guidelines and procedures that relate to the implementation of safe and secure learning environments for learners, advocate and facilitate the use of effective practices to foster learning environments that promote fairness, respect and care to encourage learning, model exemplary practices in the management of classroom structure and activities, and lead colleagues at the whole-school level to review and evaluate their practices, facilitate processes to review the effectiveness of the school's learning environment to nurture and inspire learner participation, lead and empower colleagues in promoting learning environments that effectively motivate learners to achieve quality outcomes by assuming responsibility for their own learning, and provide leadership in applying a wide range of strategies in the implementation of positive and non-violent discipline policies/procedures to ensure learning-focused environments.

The findings agree with Laude et al. (2018). According to them master teachers have the potential and capability to lead their respective school particularly in improving the academic performance of the students and giving technical assistance to their colleagues.

Table 23
Dominant domain in the instructional competence according to Master Teachers, School Head and Teachers

PARTICIPANTS	INSTRUCTIONAL COMPETENCE OF MASTER TEACHERS	MEAN RANK	RANK	FRIEDMAN STATISTICS	P VALUE	REMARKS
Master Teacher	Mastery of the Subject Matter	2.55	1.5	2.000	0.572	Accept Ho
	Teaching Strategy Skills	2.45	3.5			
	Classroom Management Skills	2.55	1.5			
	Evaluation Skills	2.45	3.5			
School Heads	Mastery of the Subject Matter	2.88	1	3.000	0.392	Accept Ho
	Teaching Strategy Skills	2.38	2.33			

Teachers	Classroom Management Skills	2.38	2.33	5.767	0.123	Accept Ho
	Evaluation Skills	2.38	2.33			
	Mastery of the Subject Matter	2.52	3			
	Teaching Strategy Skills	2.39	4			
	Classroom Management Skills	2.56	1			
	Evaluation Skills	2.54	2			
	<hr/>					
TOTAL	MASTERY OF THE SUBJECT MATTER	2.53	2	6.582	0.086	ACCEPT HO
	TEACHING STRATEGY SKILLS	2.39	4			
	CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT SKILLS	2.55	1			
	EVALUATION SKILLS	2.52	3			

Mean rank followed by a common letter are not significant at 5% level

Table 23 shows the dominant domain in the instructional competence of master teachers according to master teachers – participants, school heads and teachers. It reveals that the dominant domain in the instructional competence according to master teacher – participants are *mastery of the subject matter* and *classroom management skills* with mean rank of 2.55 respectively, these domains rank, *first*. The same domain is revealed as dominant on the assessment of school head, *mastery of subject matter* with mean rank of 2.88.

According to teachers, the dominant domain is *classroom management* with mean rank of 2.56, it is rank, *first*. This domain is distinct as observe by the teachers since master teachers observe classes of teachers, apparently this domain is being modelled by the master teachers. This also proves the findings of Laude et al. (2018) that master teachers

has the potential to lead their colleagues when it comes to Instructional Competence particularly on the classroom management.

On the other hand, the findings contradict the findings of Romero (2019), in her study on The Transformation of the Master Teachers in the Schools Division of Catanduanes, it was revealed that problems encountered by the master teachers was they lack the required skills and competence in conducting instructional supervision. The findings of this study as observe by the master teacher – participants, school head and teachers, their dominant domain are mastery of the subject matter and classroom management skills.

Table 24
Significant difference on instructional leadership practices of master teachers when group according to sex

INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP PRACTICES	SEX	MEDIAN	MEAN RANK	MANN-WHITNEY U STATISTICS	P VALUE	REMARKS
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	Male	4.00	11.36	32.500	0.344	Accept Ho
	Female	4.00	9.21			
Learning Environment	Male	4.00	8.21	29.500	0.255	Accept Ho
	Female	4.75	11.04			
Diversity of Learners	Male	4.00	9.79	40.500	0.891	Accept Ho
	Female	4.00	10.13			
Curriculum Planning	Male	4.00	9.86	41.000	0.924	Accept Ho
	Female	4.50	10.08			
Assessment and Reporting	Male	5.00	10.00	42.000	1.000	Accept Ho
	Female	4.75	10.00			
	Male	5.00	9.14	36.000	0.568	Accept Ho

Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	Female	5.00	10.50			
Personal Growth and Professional Development	Male	5.00	9.43	38.000	0.686	Accept Ho
	Female	5.00	10.33			
TOTAL	MALE	4.50	9.71	40.000	0.852	ACCEPT HO
	FEMALE	4.75	10.17			

Table 24 shows the significant difference on instructional leadership practices of master teachers when group according to sex. It reveals that the instructional leadership practices on content knowledge and pedagogy (p-value = 0.344), learning environment (p-value = 0.255), diversity of learners (p-value = 0.891), curriculum planning (p-value = 0.924), assessment and reporting (p-value = 1.000), community linkages and professional engagement (p-value = 0.568) and professional growth and professional development (p-value = 0.686) have no significant difference in terms of sex. The total p-value is 0.852. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The result of the study supports the findings of Sangalang (2018) that the variable sex was not factor in defining the level of technical assistance provided by the master teachers. When master teachers give technical assistance it should be based on the PPST standard.

Table 25

Significant difference on instructional leadership practices of master teachers when group according age

INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP PRACTICES	AGE	MEDIAN	MEAN RANK	KRUSKAL-WALLIS STATISTICS	P VALUE	REMARKS
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	40 and below	4.50	12.00	1.102	0.576	Accept Ho
	41 to 49	4.00	8.94			
	50 and above	4.00	10.07			

	40 and below	4.50	10.75			
Learning Environment	41 to 49	4.50	9.75	0.106	0.948	Accept Ho
	50 and above	4.50	9.86			
	40 and below	4.00	9.38			
Diversity of Learners	41 to 49	4.00	9.94	0.105	0.949	Accept Ho
	50 and above	4.50	10.43			
	40 and below	4.50	10.50			
Curriculum Planning	41 to 49	4.50	10.50	0.326	0.850	Accept Ho
	50 and above	4.00	9.14			
	40 and below	4.75	10.25			
Assessment and Reporting	41 to 49	4.50	9.25	0.315	0.854	Accept Ho
	50 and above	5.00	10.71			
	40 and below	4.50	9.50			
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	41 to 49	4.50	8.63	1.613	0.447	Accept Ho
	50 and above	5.00	11.86			

Personal Growth and Professional Development	40 and below	4.50	8.75	2.296	0.317	Accept Ho
	41 to 49	4.50	8.75			
	50 and above	5.00	12.14			
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TOTAL	40 AND BELOW	4.50	9.75	0.078	0.962	ACCEPT HO
	41 TO 49	4.50	9.75			
	50 AND ABOVE	4.50	10.43			
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Table 25 shows the significant difference on instructional leadership practices of master teachers when group according to age. It reveals that the instructional leadership practices on content knowledge and pedagogy (p-value = 0.576), learning environment (p-value = 0.948), diversity of learners (p-value = 0.949), curriculum planning (p-value = 0.850), assessment and reporting (p-value = 0.854), community linkages and professional engagement (p-value = 0.447) and professional growth and professional development (p-value = 0.317) have no significant difference in terms of age. The total p-value is 0.962. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The results of the study contradicts the findings of Sangalang (2018). According to the author, age is a factor in defining the level of technical assistance provided by the master teachers, as the master teacher grow older, there is a tendency that their level of technical assistance goes lower. However, according to the finding of this study, most of them are in their 40's but it shows that there is no significant difference on their instructional leadership practices.

Likewise, the result of the study oppose the study of Vlachad and Ferla (2013). Teacher disagreed that the age group '36-45' was less engaged in school leadership procedures.

Table 26

Significant difference on instructional leadership practices of Master Teachers when group according educational attainment

INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP PRACTICES	EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	MEDIAN	MEAN RANK	KRUSKAL-WALLIS STATISTICS	P VALUE	REMARKS
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	Master's Degree	4.00	9.30	4.085	0.130	Accept Ho
	Doctorate Units	4.00	8.65			
	Doctorate Degree	5.00	14.25			
Learning Environment	Master's Degree	4.00	7.10	2.781	0.249	Accept Ho
	Doctorate Units	4.75	10.30			
	Doctorate Degree	5.00	12.88			
Diversity of Learners	Master's Degree	4.00	10.00	0.013	0.994	Accept Ho
	Doctorate Units	4.00	9.90			
	Doctorate Degree	4.50	10.25			
Curriculum Planning	Master's Degree	4.00	7.80	1.428	0.490	Accept Ho
	Doctorate Units	4.50	10.50			
	Doctorate Degree	5.00	11.50			
Assessment and Reporting	Master's Degree	4.50	9.80	0.246	0.884	Accept Ho
	Doctorate Units	4.75	9.65			
	Doctorate Degree	5.00	11.13			

	Master's Degree	4.50	9.20			
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	Doctorate Units	5.00	9.70	0.655	0.721	Accept Ho
	Doctorate Degree	5.00	11.75			
	Master's Degree	5.00	9.70			
Personal Growth and Professional Development	Doctorate Units	5.00	9.70	0.289	0.865	Accept Ho
	Doctorate Degree	5.00	11.13			
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	MASTER'S DEGREE	4.00	7.60			
TOTAL	DOCTORATE UNITS	4.75	10.25	2.002	0.368	ACCEPT HO
	DOCTORATE DEGREE	5.00	12.38			
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Table 26 shows the significant difference on instructional leadership practices of master teachers when group according to educational attainment. . It reveals that the instructional leadership practices on content knowledge and pedagogy (p-value = 0.130), learning environment (p-value = 0.249), diversity of learners (p-value = 0.994), curriculum planning (p-value = 0.490), assessment and reporting (p-value = 0.884), community linkages and professional engagement (p-value = 0.721) and professional growth and professional development (p-value = 0.865) have no significant difference in terms of educational attainment. The total p-value is 0.368. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The results can be claimed that according to the findings, master teachers' educational level had no effect on their instructional leadership practices. It does not demonstrate that those who have previously completed their doctoral degree perform better than those who have not and simply have a master's degree. When it comes to fulfilling their duties and responsibilities as master teachers, they are on the same level.

It approves the findings of Vlachad and Ferla (2013), that the educational background of the participants in their study did not influence their distributed leadership participation, as no disparities were discovered in leaderships' dimensions

Table 27

Significant difference on instructional leadership practices of master teachers when group according field of specialization

INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP PRACTICES	FIELD OF SPECIALIZATION	MEDIAN	MEAN RANK	MANN-WHITNEY U STATISTICS	P VALUE	REMARKS
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	Math and Science	4.00	9.75	39.000	0.765	Accept Ho
	Others	4.00	10.43			
Learning Environment	Math and Science	4.00	9.17	32.000	0.363	Accept Ho
	Others	5.00	11.43			
Diversity of Learners	Math and Science	4.00	9.79	39.500	0.820	Accept Ho
	Others	4.00	10.36			
Curriculum Planning	Math and Science	4.00	8.58	25.000	0.106	Accept Ho
	Others	5.00	12.43			
Assessment and Reporting	Math and Science	4.50	9.13	31.500	0.331	Accept Ho
	Others	5.00	11.50			
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	Math and Science	4.75	9.75	39.000	0.775	Accept Ho
	Others	5.00	10.43			
Personal Growth and Professional Development	Math and Science	5.00	9.54	36.500	0.578	Accept Ho

	Others	5.00	10.79			
TOTAL	MATH AND SCIENCE	4.25	8.83	28.000	0.191	ACCEPT HO
	OTHERS	5.00	12.00			

Table 27 shows the significant difference on instructional leadership practices of master teachers when group according to field of specialization. It reveals that the instructional leadership practices on content knowledge and pedagogy (p-value = 0.765), learning environment (p-value = 0.363), diversity of learners (p-value = 0.820), curriculum planning (p-value = 0.106), assessment and reporting (p-value = 0.331), community linkages and professional engagement (p-value = 0.775) and professional growth and professional development (p-value = 0.578) have no significant difference in terms of field of specialization. The significant difference on instructional leadership practices of master teachers when group according field of specialization total p-value is 0.191, therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The results implies that the field of specialization has nothing to do with the instructional leadership practices of master teachers. However in the study of Nbina (2012), it revealed that Chemistry students taught by qualified teachers performed significantly better than those taught by unqualified teachers.

Master teachers performs their roles and responsibilities as master teachers well regardless of their field of specialization.

Table 28

Significant difference on instructional leadership practices of master teachers when group according to length of service

INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP PRACTICES	LENGTH OF SERVICE	MEDIAN	MEAN RANK	KRUSKAL-WALLIS STATISTICS	P VALUE	REMARKS
	5 and below	4.00	10.50			
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	6 to 10	4.00	11.50	2.365	0.500	Accept Ho
	11 to 15	4.00	8.13			
	16 and above	4.00	7.50			
Learning Environment	5 and below	5.00	10.83	0.170	0.982	Accept Ho

	6 to 10	4.00	9.83			
	11 to 15	4.50	9.38			
	16 and above	4.50	10.50			
	5 and below	4.50	12.00			
Diversity of Learners	6 to 10	4.00	8.94	0.891	0.828	Accept Ho
	11 to 15	4.25	10.75			
	16 and above	4.00	10.17			
	5 and below	5.00	12.00			
Curriculum Planning	6 to 10	4.00	9.44	0.751	0.861	Accept Ho
	11 to 15	4.50	10.50			
	16 and above	4.00	9.00			
	5 and below	5.00	11.00			
Assessment and Reporting	6 to 10	4.50	8.78	2.029	0.566	Accept Ho
	11 to 15	5.00	12.88			
	16 and above	4.50	8.83			
	5 and below	5.00	9.83			
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	6 to 10	4.50	8.94	1.016	0.797	Accept Ho
	11 to 15	5.00	11.75			
	16 and above	5.00	11.00			
	5 and below	5.00	10.33			
Personal Growth and Professional Development	6 to 10	5.00	9.28	0.470	0.925	Accept Ho
	11 to 15	5.00	11.13			
	16 and above	5.00	10.33			

	5 AND BELOW	5.00	11.50			
TOTAL	6 TO 10	4.00	9.17	0.667	0.881	ACCEPT HO
	11 TO 15	4.75	11.00			
	16 AND ABOVE	4.50	9.67			

Table 28 shows the significant difference on instructional leadership practices of master teachers when group according to length of service. It reveals that the instructional leadership practices on content knowledge and pedagogy (p-value = 0.500), learning environment (p-value = 0.982), diversity of learners (p-value = 0.828), curriculum planning (p-value = 0.861), assessment and reporting (p-value = 0.566), community linkages and professional engagement (p-value = 0.797) and professional growth and professional development (p-value = 0.925) have no significant difference in terms of length of service. The total p-value is 881. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The findings indicate that master teachers, regardless of their length of service, are demonstrating relatively consistent levels of competence across the different domains examined. This suggests that the development of instructional leadership skills may not be heavily dependent on the length of service alone.

The results approves the findings of Sangalang (2018), that length of service and years in service of master teachers has no significant difference between mentoring skills.

Table 29
Significant difference on instructional leadership practices of master teachers when group according training hours

INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP PRACTICES	TRAINING HOURS	MEDIAN	MEAN RANK	KRUSKAL-WALLIS STATISTICS	P VALUE	REMARKS
	47 hours and below	4.00	8.40			
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	48 to 71 hours	4.00	8.33	4.722	0.094	Accept Ho
	72 hours and above	5.00	13.50			

	47 hours and below	4.00	7.75			
Learning Environment	48 to 71 hours	5.00	12.17	3.928	0.140	Accept Ho
	72 hours and above	5.00	12.67			
	47 hours and below	4.00	7.80			
Diversity of Learners	48 to 71 hours	4.00	10.17	4.592	0.101	Accept Ho
	72 hours and above	4.75	13.58			
	47 hours and below	4.00	7.30 b			
Curriculum Planning	48 to 71 hours	5.00	12.00 ab	6.336	0.042	Reject Ho
	72 hours and above	5.00	13.50 a			
	47 hours and below	4.25	7.00 b			
Assessment and Reporting	48 to 71 hours	5.00	11.00 ab	8.120	0.017	Reject Ho
	72 hours and above	5.00	14.50 a			
	47 hours and below	4.00	7.30 b			
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	48 to 71 hours	5.00	11.00 ab	6.884	0.032	Reject Ho
	72 hours and above	5.00	14.00 a			
	47 hours and below	4.00	7.80			
Personal Growth and Professional Development	48 to 71 hours	5.00	10.33	5.514	0.063	Accept Ho
	72 hours and above	5.00	13.50			

	47 HOURS AND BELOW	4.00	7.10 B			
TOTAL	48 TO 71 HOURS	5.00	11.50 AB	7.350	0.025	REJECT HO
	72 HOURS AND ABOVE	5.00	14.08 A			

Table 29 shows the significant difference on instructional leadership practices of master teachers when group according to training hours. It reveals that the instructional leadership practices when group according to training hours on content knowledge and pedagogy (p-value = 0.094), learning environment (p-value = 0.140), diversity of learners (p-value = 0.101), and Personal Growth and Professional Development (p-value=0.063.) have no significant difference. Whereas, on curriculum planning (p-value = 0.42), assessment and reporting (p-value= 0.117) and Community Linkages and Professional Engagement (p-vale = 0.025) have significant difference. Overall the total p-value is 0.025. Therefore, hypothesis is accepted, training hours of master teacher on instructional leadership is significant.

Based on these findings, it can be claimed that training hours have a varying impact on different aspects of instructional leadership practices. While some domains do not show a significant difference, others do indicate a notable influence based on the amount of training received. This underscores the importance of targeted and relevant training in specific areas to enhance instructional leadership practices effectively.

The results approves the finding of Arnejo et al. (2018) that trainings of teachers is significant. According to their findings training intervention delivered a comprehensive program that enhances master teachers' personalities and professional conduct as teachers and instructional leaders. Thus, Master teachers require training and development to improve their leadership abilities and administrative functions.

Table 30

Significant difference on instructional leadership practices of master teachers when group according performance

INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP PRACTICES	PERFORMANC E	MEDIAN	MEAN RANK	MANN-WHITNEY U STATISTICS	P VALUE	REMAR KS
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	Very Satisfactory	4.00	8.79	33.500	0.397	Accept Ho
	Outstanding	4.00	10.71			

Learning Environment	Very Satisfactory	4.00	8.36	30.500	0.295	Accept Ho
	Outstanding	5.00	10.96			
Diversity of Learners	Very Satisfactory	4.00	9.00	35.000	0.524	Accept Ho
	Outstanding	4.25	10.58			
Curriculum Planning	Very Satisfactory	4.00	8.57	32.000	0.342	Accept Ho
	Outstanding	5.00	10.83			
Assessment and Reporting	Very Satisfactory	4.00	7.57	25.000	0.116	Accept Ho
	Outstanding	5.00	11.42			
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	Very Satisfactory	4.00	7.07	21.500	0.051	Accept Ho
	Outstanding	5.00	11.71			
Personal Growth and Professional Development	Very Satisfactory	4.00	6.71	19.000	0.020	Reject Ho
	Outstanding	5.00	11.92			
TOTAL	VERY SATISFACTORY	4.00	7.50	24.500	0.102	ACCEPT HO
	OUTSTANDING	5.00	11.46			

Table 30 shows the significant difference on instructional leadership practices of master teachers when group according to performance. It reveals that the instructional leadership practices on content knowledge and pedagogy (p-value = 0.397), learning environment (p-value = 0.295), diversity of learners (p-value = 0.524), curriculum planning (p-value = 0.342), assessment and reporting (p-value = 0.116), community linkages and professional engagement (p-value = 0.051) have no significant difference their performance. Whereas on professional growth and professional development (p-value = 0.20) have significant difference on performance. The total p-value is 0.102. Therefore,

the null hypothesis is accepted.

Furthermore, performance of master teachers in terms of instructional leadership practices were not significantly different. The result of the performance of the master teachers based on their IPCRF were very satisfactory and outstanding. This further implies that their learners have varying degrees of development and are skilled in achieving success.

However, in terms of personal growth and professional development, the results imply that there is a significant difference in performance. This finding opposes the study of Aquino et al. (2021), based on their findings, regardless of educational attainment, exemplary accomplishment, the output of the teachers remain the same.

According to the findings of this study, master teachers who actively engage in professional growth opportunities such as seminars and continuing education outperform those who do not.

Table 31

Significant difference on instructional competence when group according to sex

INSTRUCTIONAL COMPETENCE	SEX	MEDIAN	MEAN RANK	MANN-WHITNEY U STATISTICS	P VALUE	REMARKS
Mastery of the Subject Matter	Male	5.00	9.64	39.500	0.691	Accept Ho
	Female	5.00	10.21			
Teaching Strategy Skills	Male	5.00	8.79	33.500	0.256	Accept Ho
	Female	5.00	10.71			
Classroom Management Skills	Male	5.00	9.64	39.500	0.691	Accept Ho
	Female	5.00	10.21			
Evaluation Skills	Male	5.00	10.14	41.000	0.894	Accept Ho
	Female	5.00	9.92			

TOTAL	MALE	5.00	9.64	39.500	0.691	ACCEPT HO
	FEMALE	5.00	10.21			

Table 31 shows the significant difference on instructional competence of master teachers when group according to sex. It reveals that the instructional competence on mastery of the subject matter (p-value = 0.691), teaching strategy skills (p-value = 0.256), classroom management skills (p-value = 0.691), and evaluation skills (p-value = 0.894), have no significant difference in terms of sex. The total p-value is 0.691. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted

The result of the study supports the findings of Sangalang (2018) that the variable sex was not factor in defining the level of technical assistance provided by the master teachers.

Moreover, the results also approves the findings of Roberto and Madrigal (2019). Their findings showed no significant difference in both the teaching standards competence and performance when the teachers were group according to sex, educational attainment, marital status, and status of employment.

It can be argued that the instructional competence of master teachers is not gender dependent.

Table 32
Significant difference on instructional competence when group according to age

INSTRUCTIONAL COMPETENCE	AGE	MEDIAN	MEAN RANK	KRUSKAL- WALLIS STATISTICS	P VALUE	REMARKS
Mastery of the Subject Matter	40 and below	5.00	11.00	0.577	0.750	Accept Ho
	41 to 49	5.00	9.81			
	50 and above	5.00	9.64			
Teaching Strategy Skills	40 and below	5.00	11.50	1.205	0.547	Accept Ho
	41 to 49	5.00	9.13			
	50 and above	5.00	10.14			
	40 and below	5.00	11.00	0.577	0.750	Accept Ho

Classroom Management Skills	41 to 49	5.00	9.81			
	50 and above	5.00	9.64			
	40 and below	5.00	11.50			
Evaluation Skills	41 to 49	5.00	10.31	1.587	0.452	Accept Ho
	50 and above	5.00	8.79			
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	40 AND BELOW	5.00	11.00			
TOTAL	41 TO 49	5.00	9.81	0.577	0.750	ACCEPT HO
	50 AND ABOVE	5.00	9.64			
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Table 32 shows the significant difference on instructional competence of master teachers when group according to age. It reveals that the instructional competence on mastery of the subject matter (p-value = 0.750), teaching strategy skills (p-value = 0.547), classroom management skills (p-value = 0.750), and evaluation skills (p-value = 0.452), have no significant difference in terms of age. The total p-value is 0.750. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The findings indicate that master teachers, regardless of their age, possess relatively consistent levels of instructional competence in the domains examined. This suggests that the development of instructional competence may not be heavily dependent on age alone.

The findings agree in the study of Sangalang (2018) that in terms of the profile variables age of master teacher was not a factor in defining the level of general and specific mentoring skills. The same with the findings of this study that there is no significant difference with the instructional competence of master teacher notably in the mastery of the subject matter, teaching strategy skills, classroom management, and evaluation skills. They may do well regardless of their age.

Table 33

Significant difference on instructional competence when group according to educational attainment

INSTRUCTIONAL COMPETENCE	EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	MEDIAN	MEAN RANK	KRUSKAL-WALLIS STATISTICS	P VALUE	REMARKS
Mastery of the Subject Matter	Master's Degree	5.00	11.00	1.403	0.496	Accept Ho
	Doctorate Units	5.00	10.05			
	Doctorate Degree	5.00	8.63			
Teaching Strategy Skills	Master's Degree	5.00	11.50	1.256	0.534	Accept Ho
	Doctorate Units	5.00	9.60			
	Doctorate Degree	5.00	9.13			
Classroom Management Skills	Master's Degree	5.00	11.00	1.403	0.496	Accept Ho
	Doctorate Units	5.00	10.05			
	Doctorate Degree	5.00	8.63			
Evaluation Skills	Master's Degree	5.00	11.50	1.256	0.534	Accept Ho
	Doctorate Units	5.00	9.60			
	Doctorate Degree	5.00	9.13			
TOTAL	MASTER'S DEGREE	5.00	11.00	1.403	0.496	ACCEPT HO

DOCTORATE UNITS	5.00	10.05
DOCTORATE DEGREE	5.00	8.63

Table 33 shows the significant difference on instructional competence of master teachers when group according to educational management. It reveals that the instructional competence on mastery of the subject matter (p-value = 0.496), teaching strategy skills (p-value = 0.534), classroom management skills (p-value = 0.496), and evaluation skills (p-value = 0.534), have no significant difference in terms of educational attainment. The total p-value is 0.496. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The findings indicate that educational attainment does not strongly influence instructional competence in the identified domains. This implies that individuals with varying levels of education can still exhibit similar levels of competence in these instructional areas.

The finding approves the findings of Vlachad and Ferla (2013) that the educational background of the participants in this study did not influence their distributed leadership participation, as no disparities were discovered in their leaderships' dimensions.

Table 34
Significant difference on instructional competence when group according to field of specialization

INSTRUCTIONAL COMPETENCE	FIELD OF SPECIALIZATION	MEDIAN	MEAN RANK	MANN- WHITNEY U STATISTICS	P VALUE	REMARKS
Mastery of the Subject Matter	Math and Science	5.00	10.21	39.500	0.691	Accept Ho
	Others	5.00	9.64			
Teaching Strategy Skills	Math and Science	5.00	10.71	33.500	0.256	Accept Ho
	Others	5.00	8.79			
Classroom Management Skills	Math and Science	5.00	10.21	39.500	0.691	Accept Ho
	Others	5.00	9.64			

Evaluation Skills	Math and Science	5.00	9.92	41.000	0.894	Accept Ho
	Others	5.00	10.14			
TOTAL	MATH AND SCIENCE	5.00	10.21	39.500	0.691	ACCEPT HO
	OTHERS	5.00	9.64			

Table 34 shows the significant difference on instructional competence of master teachers when group according to field of specialization. It reveals that the instructional competence on mastery of the subject matter (p-value = 0.691), teaching strategy skills (p-value = 0.256), classroom management skills (p-value = 0.691), and evaluation skills (p-value = 0.894), have no significant difference in terms of field of specialization. The total is p-value = 0.691. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The results imply that the field of specialization has nothing to do with the instructional competence of master teachers. However in the study of Nbina (2012), it revealed that Chemistry students taught by qualified teachers performed significantly better than those taught by unqualified teachers. Therefore, field of specialization has still factor when it comes to instructional competence.

Nevertheless, Master teachers performs their roles and responsibilities as master teachers well regardless of their field of specialization.

Table 35

Significant difference on instructional competence when group according to length of service

INSTRUCTIONAL COMPETENCE	LENGTH OF SERVICE	MEDIAN	MEAN RANK	KRUSKAL-WALLIS STATISTICS	P VALUE	REMARKS
Mastery of the Subject Matter	5 and below	5.00	11.00	2.353	0.502	Accept Ho
	6 to 10	5.00	8.89			
	11 to 15	5.00	11.00			
	16 and above	5.00	11.00			
Teaching Strategy Skills	5 and below	5.00	8.33	2.167	0.539	Accept Ho
	6 to 10	5.00	9.39			
	11 to 15	5.00	11.50			

	16 and above	5.00	11.50			
	5 and below	5.00	11.00			
Classroom Management Skills	6 to 10	5.00	8.89	2.353	0.502	Accept Ho
	11 to 15	5.00	11.00			
	16 and above	5.00	11.00			
	5 and below	5.00	8.33			
Evaluation Skills	6 to 10	5.00	9.39	2.167	0.539	Accept Ho
	11 to 15	5.00	11.50			
	16 and above	5.00	11.50			
	5 AND BELOW	5.00	11.00			
TOTAL	6 TO 10	5.00	8.89	2.353	0.502	ACCEPT HO
	11 TO 15	5.00	11.00			
	16 AND ABOVE	5.00	11.00			

Table 35 shows the significant difference on instructional competence of master teachers when group according to length of service. It reveals that the instructional competence on mastery of the subject matter (p-value = 0.691), teaching strategy skills (p-value = 0.256), classroom management skills (p-value = 0.691), and evaluation skills (p-value = 0.894), have no significant difference in terms of length of service. The total p-value is 0.691. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The results approves the findings of Sangalang (2018), that length of service and years in service of master teachers has no significant difference between mentoring skills.

Table 36
Significant difference on instructional competence when group according to training hours

INSTRUCTIONAL COMPETENCE	TRAINING HOURS	MEDIAN	MEAN RANK	KRUSKAL-WALLIS STATISTICS	P VALUE	REMARKS
Mastery of the Subject Matter	47 hours and below	5.00	9.10	1.906	0.386	Accept Ho
	48 to 71 hours	5.00	11.00			
	72 hours and above	5.00	11.00			
Teaching Strategy Skills	47 hours and below	5.00	8.65	3.038	0.219	Accept Ho
	48 to 71 hours	5.00	11.50			
	72 hours and above	5.00	11.50			
Classroom Management Skills	47 hours and below	5.00	9.10	1.906	0.386	Accept Ho
	48 to 71 hours	5.00	11.00			
	72 hours and above	5.00	11.00			
Evaluation Skills	47 hours and below	5.00	9.60	0.663	0.718	Accept Ho
	48 to 71 hours	5.00	11.50			
	72 hours and above	5.00	9.92			
	47 HOURS AND BELOW	5.00	9.10			
TOTAL	48 TO 71 HOURS	5.00	11.00	1.906	0.386	ACCEPT HO
	72 HOURS AND ABOVE	5.00	11.00			

Table 37 shows the significant difference on instructional competence of master teachers when group according to training hours. It reveals that the instructional competence on mastery of the subject matter (p-value = 0.386), teaching strategy skills (p-value = 0.219), classroom management skills (p-value = 0.386), and evaluation skills (p-value = 0.718), have no significant difference in terms of length of service. The total p-value is 0.386. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The results contradicts with the findings of Arnejo et al. (2018) that trainings of teachers

is significant. According to their findings training intervention delivered a comprehensive program that enhances master teachers' personalities and professional conduct as teachers and instructional leaders. Based on the results of this study trainings hours has no significant difference with instructional competence of master teachers.

Table 37
Significant difference on instructional competence when group according to performance

INSTRUCTIONAL COMPETENCE	PERFORMANCE	MEDIAN	MEAN RANK	MANN-WHITNEY U STATISTICS	P VALUE	REMARKS
Mastery of the Subject Matter	Vary Satisfactory	5.00	9.64	39.500	0.691	Accept Ho
	Outstanding	5.00	10.21			
Teaching Strategy Skills	Vary Satisfactory	5.00	10.14	41.000	0.894	Accept Ho
	Outstanding	5.00	9.92			
Classroom Management Skills	Vary Satisfactory	5.00	9.64	39.500	0.691	Accept Ho
	Outstanding	5.00	10.21			
Evaluation Skills	Vary Satisfactory	5.00	10.14	41.000	0.894	Accept Ho
	Outstanding	5.00	9.92			
TOTAL	VARY SATISFACTORY	5.00	9.64	39.500	0.691	ACCEPT HO
	OUTSTANDING	5.00	10.21			

Table 37 shows the significant difference on instructional competence of master teachers when group according to performance. It reveals that the instructional competence on mastery of the subject matter (p-value = 0.691), teaching strategy skills (p-value = 0.894), classroom management skills (p-value = 0.691), and evaluation skills (p-value = 0.894), have no significant difference in terms of performance. The total p-value is 0.691. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

According to Mendoza and Baustista (2022) the greater the performance of master teachers in their instructional leadership practices, the more instructionally competent the

respondents were. However the findings of this study revealed that the instructional leadership practices of master teachers and instructional competency skills of senior high school teachers had little to do with their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF).

It is then beneficial for the master teachers to attend seminars, workshops, and enhancement trainings to improve and sustain their instructional leadership practices and competence skills.

Table 38
Significant relationship between the instructional leadership practices and instructional competence of Master Teachers

INSTRUCTIONAL COMPETENCE	INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP PRACTICES	SPEARMAN RANK	P-VALUE	REMARKS
Mastery of the Subject Matter	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	0.602	0.000	Reject Ho
Teaching Strategy Skills	Learning Environment	0.638	0.000	Reject Ho
Classroom Management Skills	Diversity of Learners	0.590	0.000	Reject Ho
	Curriculum Planning	0.631	0.000	Reject Ho
Evaluation Skills	Assessment and Reporting	0.597	0.000	Reject Ho
	Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	0.549	0.000	Reject Ho
	Personal Growth and Professional Development	0.628	0.000	Reject Ho
TOTAL		0.627	0.000	REJECT HO

Table 38 shows the results of the significant relationship between the instructional leadership practices and instructional competence of master teachers. The Spearman Rank Correlation with p- value of 0.000 was used to determine the significant relationship between the instructional leadership practices and instructional competence of master teachers.

The result reveals that that the instructional leadership practices and instructional competence of master teachers has significant relationship.

The results of the study claims that the instructional leadership practices performed by

the master teachers are based on the standard set by Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). They possess the characteristics described in the seven domains (PPST) that are required by teachers to be effective in the 21st Century in the Philippines; content knowledge and pedagogy, diversity of learners, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting, community linkages and professional engagement, and personal growth and professional development.

In consequence, master teachers demonstrate highly competent and performing in terms of instructional competence; mastery of the subject matter, teaching strategy skills, classroom management skills and evaluation skills. Thus, they are qualified as leaders.

The findings agree with the findings of Mendoza and Bautista (2022), that the master teachers have very good instructional leadership practices in terms of curriculum content and pedagogy, planning, assessment and reporting, and personal growth and personal development. Moreover, Senior High School teachers' instructional competence skills showed "Highly Proficient" in terms of their mastery of the subject matter, teaching strategies, classroom management, and evaluation.

Conclusions

Based on the findings identified and revealed in this study, the following conclusions were made:

1. The demographic profile of the master teachers in terms of sex, majority of them are female, aged 41 to 49, most them have Doctorate units with specialization in science and mathematics, have 6 to 10 years length of service, have attended instructional leadership trainings of 47 hours and below, and have outstanding performance in their IPCRF.
2. Master Teachers often practiced all the indicators of the seven domains of the Philippine Professional Standard for Teacher to a high extent.
3. The level of instructional competence are highly competent. Master teachers possess a high level of expertise in instructional strategies, methodologies, and approaches. Their competence indicates that they have a deep understanding of effective teaching practices and are skilled in applying them in the classroom.
4. The dominant domain in the instructional leadership practices of master teachers is personal growth and professional development since majority of them have Doctorate units. The master teachers prioritize their personal growth and professional development, as evidenced by their pursuit of Doctorate units. Their commitment to ongoing learning suggests a dedication to staying current with the latest research, theories, and practices in their respective fields.
5. The dominant domain their instructional competence is classroom management. Master teachers demonstrate a high level of proficiency in creating and maintaining positive and well-managed classroom environments. Their expertise in classroom

management contributes to a conducive learning atmosphere where students feel safe, engaged, and motivated to participate actively in their learning.

6. The instructional leadership practices of master teachers have no significant difference with sex with age, educational attainment, field of specialization, length of service, and performance. However, training hours is significant. Moreover, instructional competence of master teachers has no significant difference with sex age, educational attainment, field of specialization, length of service, training hours and performance.

7. The instructional leadership practices and instructional competence of master teachers is highly significant. Master teachers demonstrate strong instructional leadership practices, which contribute to their overall instructional competence. Their ability to lead and guide others in effective teaching practices enhances their own instructional skills and the instructional practices of the educational institution as a whole.

Recommendations

Following a comprehensive evaluation and interpretation of the study's findings, the following are strongly suggested:

1. Schools may encourage continuous professional development to master teachers by providing opportunities for further specialization and training in science and mathematics education, as well as instructional leadership. Recognize and utilize their expertise through leveraging their knowledge and experience by assigning them as mentors or resource persons for other teachers. They can provide guidance, support, and share best practices in science and mathematics education. In addition schools may create platforms or structures that encourage collaboration and knowledge sharing among the master teachers and their peers. This could be through subject-specific groups, communities of practice, or professional learning communities where they can discuss innovative teaching methods and share resources.

2. Indicators in the Philippine Professional Standard may be utilized and observed properly by the master teachers since they were assessed by teachers as high extent. Re-orient the master teachers with the characteristics of a master teacher as described in the seven domains of the PPST.

3. Schools may encourage master teachers to engage in ongoing professional development to stay updated with the latest research, teaching strategies, and educational technologies. This can be done through participation in conferences, workshops, webinars, or online courses. Moreover, master teachers may engage in research and innovation in their respective fields. This can involve conducting action research projects, exploring new teaching methodologies, or developing innovative instructional materials. School Division Office may provide support and resources for their research endeavors.

4. Schools may utilize the leadership skills of master teachers who already have

Doctorate degree in conducting school-based training workshops, such as in-service trainings, school learning action cell or focus group discussion for teachers. This will enable them to share their knowledge and insights, provide guidance, and support the professional growth of their mentees.

5. Master teachers may also invite teachers I to III to observe their classes, in this way they can demonstrate their best classroom practices and strategies. In consequence, teachers may adopt these practices in their own classrooms. This would promote a culture of peer support where teachers can observe and learn from one another, exchange ideas, and provide feedback. Moreover, this would lead to the improvement of teaching and learning process.

6. The Department of Education may consider number of hours in providing trainings for master teachers, the more trainings attended, the more knowledge and skills they will be gained. Since, statistically showed a significant in instructional leadership practices and training hours.

7. Schools Division Office may conduct capacity building for master teachers in strengthening the instructional leadership practices and instructional competence of master teachers aligned with the Philippine Professional Standard for Teachers focusing on the least instructional leadership practices such as curriculum planning, diversity of learner, and community linkages and professional engagement using the proposed learning and development plan.

8. Researchers may conduct research study in instructional leadership practices and instructional competence of master teachers in private schools.

9. Researchers may conduct a qualitative research on the perception of school heads, master teachers and teachers on instructional leadership and instructional competence of master teachers that will validate the present findings of the study. Also they may utilize a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship between instructional leadership practices, instructional competence, and their impact on student learning.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered ethical considerations on the conduct of the study and to the Republic Act 10173, also known as Data Privacy Act of 2012. An informed consent letter was sent to the participants. The researcher also informed the participants on the purpose of the study. Moreover, protection of the privacy of the research participants and adequate level of confidentiality was ensured. Furthermore, result and findings of this study will only be shared to research conferences and research journals. Lastly, participation of the respondents in this study was voluntary and they have the rights to withdraw from the study at any stage if they wish to do so.

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REFERENCES

- Aquino, C. J. C. A., Afalla, B. T. A., & Fabelico, F. L. F. (2021, December). Managing Educational Institution: School Heads' Leadership Practices and teachers' Performance. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*.
- Camahalan, S., & Naparan, G. (2022). Teachers' Use of Academic Research Databases and its Relationship to their Research Skills and Performance. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Education Research*, 24–37. <https://doi.org/10.24289/ijsser.1127770>
- Collins Owusu-Fordjour (2022). "Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Integrated Science Teachers and Its Impact on Their Instructional Practice." *American Journal of*

- Educational Research, vol. 10, no. 7 (2022): 439-443. doi: 10.12691/education-10-7-2.
- Cordova, W. M., & Linaugo, J. D. (2022). Pedagogical Content Knowledge Practices of Public School Science Teachers. *Technique Soc. Sci. J.*, 37, 37.
- Crossman, A. (2020, March 19). Understanding Purposive Sampling An Overview of the Method and Its Applications. *Tought Co.* Retrieved October 7, 2022, from <https://www.thoughtco.com/purposive-sampling-3026727>
- Dhal, P. K. (2021). Women and Teaching Profession Women and Teaching Profession. *ResearchGate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348659577_Women_and_Teaching_Profession_Women_and_Teaching_Profession
- Department of Education Instructional Supervision: Standards, Procedures, and Tools Handbook DepEd Order (DO) No. 2, s. 2015 Guidelines on the Establishment and Implementation of the Result- Based Performance Management System (RPMS) DepEd Order (DO) No.42, s. 2017 National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers
- Echeche, G. M. (2022). Coaching and Mentoring Practices of Master Teachers towards Effective Teaching. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, ISSN: 2319-7064 SJIF (2022): 7.942(ISSN: 2319-7064). <https://www.ijsr.net/archive/v11i7/SR22630083559.pdf>
- Essien, E. E., Akpan, O. E., & Obot, I. M. (2016). The Influence of In-Service Training, Seminars and Workshops Attendance by Social Studies Teachers on Academic Performance of Students in Junior Secondary Schools In Cross River State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, Vol.7,(22).
- Ibrahim, N., Aziz, A. H. A., & Nambiar, R. M. K. (2013). What Master Teachers Do: A Case Study of Planning, Facilitating, Role Modeling and Developing Materials. *Eric*. Retrieved March 2, 2022, from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1068405.pdf>
- Jacob, F. John, S., & Gwany, D. M. (2020). Teachers' Pedagogical Content Knowledge and Students' Academic Achievement: A theoretical Overview. *Journal of Global Research in Education and Social Science*, 14–44.
- Laude, L. M., Ralar, T. J. T., & Arcenal, J. T. (2018). Master Teachers as Instructional Leaders: An Exploration of School Leadership Capacity in the Division of Biliran. *International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research (IJSBAR)*, 40(1).
- Lappe, J. M. (2000). Taking the mystery out of research: Descriptive Correlational Design. *Orthopedic Nursing*, 19(2), 81.
- Lucero, J. (2018). Instructional Competence of Master Teachers: Basis for Learning Action Cell Sessions. *International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning*, Vol. 5(Issue 4, pp: (5-8)). [https://www.noveltyjournals.com/upload/paper/INSTRUCTIONAL%20COMPETE NCE-1425.pdf](https://www.noveltyjournals.com/upload/paper/INSTRUCTIONAL%20COMPETE%20NCE-1425.pdf)
- Mendoza, J. J., & Bautista, S. C. (2022, May). Master Teachers' Leadership Practices, Instructional Competence and Performance of Senior High Teachers in the City Divisions of Laguna. *International Journal of Social Science and Education Research Studies*
- Mc. Clean, W. A. (2009). The Master Teacher: Role and responsibilities in the reform process. Retrieved from <http://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED505868.pdf>. March 2, 2022
- Moore, F. (2015). The Role of Research in Developing Teachers Problems Solving Skills. *Journal of Teacher Education*
- Nbina, J. B. (2012). Teachers' Competence and Students' Academic Performance in Senior Secondary Schools Chemistry: Is There Any Relationship?? *Global Journal of Educational Research*, 11(1), 15–18.
- Paciona, A. (2019, January 18). An Assessment of The Teacher's Professional Competencies in Mataas Na Pulo Elementary School: Basis for The Implementation of an Action

- Plan. <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/AAJMRA/article/view/7700>
- Podador, F. (2023). Instructional Supervision and Leadership Skills of Master Teachers in the Division of Manila: Input for an Enhancement Training Program. *GEO Academic Journal*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.56738/issn29603986.geo2023.4.29>
- Potane, J., Arnejo, J., & Alforte, N. (2021). Phases of Collaboration in Exploring Master Teachers' Competence. *International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research (IJSBAR)*, 60(5), 173-188.
- Roberto, J. R., & Madrigal, D. V. M. (2019, March). Teacher Quality in the Light of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers. *Research Gate*. Retrieved April 22, 2023, from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332103677_Teacher_Quality_in_the_Light_of_the_Philippine_Professional_Standards_for_Teachers
- Romero, M. J. (2019). The Transformation of the Master Teachers in the Schools Division of Catanduanes. *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts*, 3(2K).
- Sangalang, L. (2018). Mentoring Skills and Technical Assistance of Master Teachers in Pangasinan. *PSU Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 1(1). Retrieved from <https://www.psurj.org/online/index.php/mrj/article/view/115>
- Vlachadi, M., & Ferla, M. (2013). Differentiation of Teachers' and Principals' Engagement in Distributed Leadership According to Their Demographic Characteristics. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 2(4), 19-30.
- Widayati, A., MacCallum, J., & Woods-McConney, A. (2021). Teachers' perceptions of continuing professional development: a study of vocational high school teachers in Indonesia. *Teacher Development*, 25(5), 604–621. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13664530.2021.1933159>
- Ülger, M., Yiğittir, S., & Ercan, O. (2014). Secondary school teachers' beliefs on character education competency. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 131, 442-449. <https://bit.ly/3Bn8nN9>